

ICE CONDITIONS IN THE PACIFIC SECTOR OF ANTARCTICA IN 2016-2025 AND ITS IMPACT ON THE TOOTHFISH FISHERY

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Antarctic seas are covered with ice for most of the year and, therefore, inaccessible to ships, the fishery is carried out in the spring-summer (for the Southern Hemisphere) period. The toothfish fishery is carried out almost exclusively in polynyas. Polynyas are regions with low sea ice concentration within high sea ice concentrations.

The following parameters were adopted to assess the degree of polynya development and their impact on the fishery.

Polynyas form off the coast of Antarctica and then spread north. The next dates are interesting:

1. The date of polynya appearance.
2. The date when the polynya reaches 75° S (in the Ross Sea) and 72°S (in the Amundsen Sea).
3. The date when the polynya reaches 70°S.
4. The date when the polynya connects to the open ocean.

In recent years, the polynya has appeared from November 9 to December 2 in the Ross Sea and from November 4 to 18 in the Amundsen Sea. When averaging, there is a tendency for the polynya to start forming later and later in both seas.

The date when the polynya reaches 72/75°S is the date when longliners can begin fishing for toothfish. This is the period from November 20 to December 17 in the Ross Sea and November 16 – January 20 in the Amundsen Sea. Here, too, there is a tendency for this event to be delayed every year.

The date when the polynya reaches 70°S characterizes the possibility of full development of the fishery in all seas. This is the period from December 28 to January 12 in the Ross Sea and from January 4 to January 28 in the Amundsen Sea, and sometimes it does not reach 70°S at all. With fairly significant fluctuations in this date, no obvious trend is observed here.

The date of the polynya's connection with the ocean characterizes the release of the sea from the main masses of ice. In the Ross Sea, this was observed on January 3–15, in the Amundsen Sea – on January 8–28, and sometimes it was not observed at all. In the Ross Sea, a downward trend is observed, that is, this phenomenon occurs earlier and earlier. In the Amundsen Sea, there is no obvious trend.

Comparing the processes of polynya development in the Ross and Amundsen Seas, we can conclude that in the former, a polynya appears earlier, develops more intensively, and the sea is better cleared of ice. In contrast, the Amundsen Sea is later and worse cleared of ice, and sometimes the polynya does not connect to the open ocean. Fishing area 88.2_1 has been inaccessible for several years due to dense ice accumulations. This largely determines the preference that fishing vessels give to the Ross Sea over the Amundsen Sea.